

TRACKING MARINE MAMMALS BY SATELLITE - STATUS AND TECHNICAL NEEDS

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ABSTRACT

Faced with exorbitant costs of staging open-ocean experiments and the difficulties of tracking marine mammals, wildlife biologists are increasingly drawn to satellite technology as a cost-effective means of studying many widely-ranging animals. Development of a small prototype NIMBUS-6 satellite transmitter pack for tracking dolphins has been completed. Many technical needs, such as conversion to the ARGOS or alternative satellite systems and size reduction of the units, remain before satellite tracking can be effectively used to study marine mammals.

1. INTRODUCTION

Developing techniques for long-term studies of marine mammals is definitely challenging. Most of the whales and dolphins, and many pinnipeds, travel over extensive areas of the world's oceans or ice-covered areas making it difficult for wildlife biologists to study them during most of their voyage. Glimpses into their life history and behavior can be obtained from conventional radiotracking but their speed, agility and dive patterns make them hard to follow because of the short-range reception of most tracking systems (Leatherwood and Evans, 1979; Butler and Jennings, 1980). It is difficult to design radio packs for animals, especially those as sleek as dolphins, that do not interfere with the animal's natural movements and behaviors. The package itself must withstand the rigors of the oceanic environment and physical stresses placed upon it by the animals. Marine mammals of several schools should be studied to draw any general conclusions about the population, but the logistics and expense of major field operations usually limit the size of the study area and, often, the number of animals which can be tracked. In the case of the eastern tropical Pacific common dolphin (*Delphinus delphis*) and the spotted dolphin (*Stenella attenuata*), the groups have been observed to disperse (Evans, 1974; Butler and Jennings, 1980). Individual spotted dolphins are capable of average daily movements of 30-50 nm (Perrin et al., 1979) making it essentially impossible to track

several dolphins for more than a few days. Conventional tracking techniques cannot provide the distribution and movement information necessary for development of management and conservation regimes for those marine mammals whose ranges are enormous; the estimated geographic range for the spotted dolphin (*Stenella attenuata*) in the eastern tropical Pacific is eight million square kilometers.

2. SATELLITE TRACKING SYSTEMS

Satellite systems exist which can allow regular monitoring of many animals, instrumented with satellite-linked transmitters, over their entire ranges. At any time during an orbit, NASA's NIMBUS-6 satellite can monitor an area about 1600 km wide with 17.55 million km² in view at any time. Signals from two hundred transmitters can be received intermittently. The satellite circles the earth every 108 minutes in a polar orbit with the best coverage at the poles and at least three good passes per day over any temperate area. Location of a transmitter is determined by calculation of Doppler frequency shifts between the transmitter and the satellite, which is moving through a known orbit. A minimum of four complete signals must be received by the satellite ("uplinks") during the pass of about 15-20 minutes for calculation of the transmitter's location. The information is then relayed to ground stations.

NIMBUS-6 requires a signal at 401.2MHz \pm 5kHz. The format of the 980 ms signal is a 360 ms unmodulated carrier followed by 620 ms of bit and frame synchronizations, platform identification, operational mode, and four data channels (Fig. 1). The full 980 ms signal is required for location determination even if no data is transmitted.

Figure 1 also depicts the transmission format for the alternate satellite system currently capable of animal tracking, the ARGOS System. It is important to note that ARGOS only requires a 360 ms segment to determine the transmitter's location. ARGOS offers better coverage with two orbiting satellites.

3. ANIMAL TRACKING STUDIES

The first attempts at tracking animals via satellite involved large radio packs worn by primarily terrestrial animals. In their pioneering work of 1970, the Craigheads tracked elk through NASA's NIMBUS-3 satellite using an 11.3-kg pack worn as a harness (Craighead et al., 1972). In the late 1970's, polar bears were tracked via NASA's NIMBUS-6 using 5-kg radio collars built by HANDAR (Kolz et al., 1980). This prototype was repackaged as a float to track a loggerhead turtle (Timko and Kolz, 1982). Attempts have been made to track basking sharks also using a towed buoy package (Priede, 1980). An international polar bear experiment continues in 1982 with 15 polar bears instrumented with ARGOS radios built by Polar Research (Mitch Taylor, pers. comm.). Attempts are being made to develop ARGOS transmitters to track large whales (Bruce Mate, pers. comm.).

Following a 5-year research and development effort, the National Marine Fisheries Service has completed a prototype design for the smallest satellite transmitter pack ever used for animal tracking (Jennings and Gandy, 1980). In June 1981, we tracked two wild Hawaiian spotted dolphins (*Stenella attenuata*) for 1 and 8 days off the Kona coast of Hawaii using NASA's NIMBUS-6 satellite.

4. DOLPHIN TRANSMITTER DESIGN

The dolphin pack weighs only 907 gm and is packaged in two connected cylinders which fit around the dolphin's dorsal fin. The tubes are approximately equal in weight to facilitate accommodation by the animal. Each cylinder housing measures 17.5 x 5 cm and is constructed of 6061 aluminum, 0.75-cm thick. The housing is anodized to resist corrosion, and hydrostatically tested to 1000 psi (204-m depth in sea water). The electronics are contained in one tube and battery pack in the other. Dimensions of the tubes were largely based on the width of the oscillator crystal and battery mass. The power supply consists of 18 3-volt organic lithium cells and a power amplifier. A one-quarter wavelength (17.8 cm) stainless steel stub antenna is used with a coiled base to allow flexibility as the animals swims and minimize the likelihood of entanglement in fishing nets.

NIMBUS-6 requirements for the RF oscillator are a medium term stability of at least one part in 10^6 over a maximum temperature slope of $1^\circ\text{C}/15$ min (4 Hz/ 15 min) and a long term stability equal to or better than 7.5 parts in 10^6 ($3\text{kHz}/\text{year}$). We have had difficulty meeting these specifications.

To conserve battery life, the main timing circuit turns the unit on for 4-hour periods at daily or weekly intervals. During these 4 hours, the transmission repetition rate is set at a predetermined interval. Immediately following this interval, transmissions are

controlled by a switch circuit which detects salt water. The next surfacing of the dolphin which exposes the antenna tip opens the circuit, triggering a delay timer. This timer delays the transmission for 100 ms to allow time for the antenna to become fully exposed and upright.

Several modifications of the original specifications have been made on the final prototype for the feasibility test as a result of analyzing wild dolphins' behavior while wearing the pack. These include moving the antenna forward, changing the delay time, and increasing the repetition rate to insure transmissions during any long surfacings. Another major change was mounting the antenna on a 17-cm pedestal to elevate it above the splash zone. Analysis of films indicated that splashing decreased the amount of time available to less than the required 980 ms. In addition, the initial signal power output of 0.5 watt was found to be marginal so it was increased to 1.0 watt. The increases in transmission rate and signal power reduced the expected life of the pack from about 44 days to about 14 days with daily 4-hour transmission periods. The antenna pedestal increased the drag on the dolphin so that long term studies would not be possible.

5. TECHNICAL NEEDS FOR MARINE MAMMAL TRACKING

NASA's NIMBUS-6 program is scheduled for cancellation in the fall of 1982. The only other currently available satellite system for animal tracking is Service ARGOS which has more stringent specifications, particularly the frequency stability requirements. As opposed to the NIMBUS-6 system which requires the full 980 ms message, Service ARGOS has the distinct advantage for animal trackers of only requiring a 360 ms segment of the transmission for location determination (Fig. 1). In the case of the dolphin transmitter, this eliminates the need for the pedestal. However, permission to use the ARGOS satellites for animal tracking is currently limited to 6-month experiments. If this remains the case, an alternative satellite-tracking system, perhaps through the Shuttle Program, should be investigated.

In order to insure location precision, Service ARGOS maintains high standards for certification specifications. However, biologists studying widely-ranging animals are willing to accept less precision on the location fixes if they can be provided with transmitter packs which are more suitable for attachment to their animals. Possible solutions we proposed at the Conference on the Use of Remote Sensing of Marine Mammals (Botkin et al., 1981) include relaxation of the specification and/or improvements of the algorithm for location determination to allow the use of less stable oscillators.

Most marine mammalogists need a reduction in the size of the pack for studies lasting beyond a couple of weeks. For dolphins, weight

should be reduced to about one pound and, equally important, the width of the housing (currently 5 cm) should be reduced by at least 2.5 cm to reduce hydrodynamic drag. This means that a smaller oscillator crystal is needed. The length of the tubes could be somewhat lengthened to allow repackaging of the batteries.

Package size is largely based on battery mass. NASA is examining ways of minimizing the number of batteries through adjustment of the duty cycles. Micro-processors could be preprogrammed to the appropriate orbits. In the case of the dolphin transmitter pack, this could reduce the transmission time from 4 hours to probably one period of 30 minutes (Chuck Cote, NASA, pers. comm.). This type of duty cycle adjustment is necessary to maximize the life of the package since many of the biological questions, such as transoceanic whale migration, require about a year's data. ARGOS' location requirement of only a 360 ms message would, of course, help minimize the power requirement. Similarly, an increase in satellite receiver sensitivity would allow lower power transmissions. Identification of more efficient battery power sources combined with micro-miniaturization of the electronics could permit fabrication of very small packages.

Ideally, a compatible set of electronics and antenna modules would be available to biologists so that the packs could be assembled for different animals in different habitats. Oscillators stabilized for arctic temperature would be available for ringed seals, small beluga whales, and large bowhead whales; alternate oscillators would be available for tropical dolphins and Hawaiian monk seals. Antennas, such as small stubs for dolphins, would be interchangeable with plate antennas for seals which inhabit rocky areas or whales which swim under the ice. Timing circuits (including duty cycles, transmission repetition timers, and delay switches) would be easily adjustable so that biologists could customize them according to the animal's behavior. The electronics and battery packs would be small enough to be packaged in various configuration to be fitted on dolphin fins, implanted in whales, or fitted on seal collars.

Most wildlife biologists are not trained in electronics and most biological research programs do not have adequate funds to pay for development of unique transmitter packs. However, 65 international marine biological programs have formally expressed the desire to use satellite tracking technology. The availability of reasonably priced, small compatible modules and low cost data would make space technology as common a tool to biologists as conventional VHF and HF tracking is today.

Finally, the environmental and biological sensors which will allow a better understanding of the habitat and the physiology of the animals during different phases of their life cycle must

be incorporated. As small "mobile buoys", marine mammals in particular could provide a wealth of information on the global ecology of much of the world's oceans.

LITERATURE CITED

- Botkin, D.B., L. Hobbs, J. Kelly, and E.V. Pecan. 1981. Marine Mammals and the Biosphere: Report of the Conference on the Use of Remote Sensing of Marine Mammals. March 21-22, 1981. Santa Barbara Institute for Environmental Studies.
- Butler, R.W. and J.G. Jennings. 1980. Radio tracking of dolphins in the eastern tropical Pacific using VHF and HF equipment. Pages 757-759 in Amlaner, C. J. and MacDonald, D.W., eds. A handbook on biotelemetry and radiotracking. Pergamon Press, Oxford.
- Craighead, F.C. Jr., Craighead, J.J., Cote, C.E. and H.K. Buechner. 1972. Satellite and ground radiotracking of elk. Pages 9-11 in S. Galler, K. Schmidt - Koenig, G. Jacobs, and R. Belleville, eds. Animal orientation and navigation: A symposium. NASA SP 262:99-111.
- Evans, W.E. 1974. Radio-telemetric studies of two species of small odontocete cetaceans. Pages 385-394 in Shevill, W.E., ed. The whale problem. Harvard Univ. Press, Cambridge.
- Jennings, J.G. and W.F. Gandy. 1980. Tracking pelagic dolphins by satellite. Pages 753-755 in Amlaner, C.J. and MacDonald, D.W., eds. A handbook on biotelemetry and radiotracking. Pergamon Press, Oxford.
- Kolz, A.L., Lentfer, J.W. and H.G. Fallek. 1980. Satellite radio tracking of polar bears instrumented in Alaska. Pages 743-752 in Amlaner, C.J. and MacDonald, D.W., eds. A handbook on biotelemetry and radiotracking. Pergamon Press, Oxford.
- Leatherwood, S. and W.E. Evans. 1979. Some recent uses and potentials of radiotelemetry in field studies of cetaceans. Pages 1-31 in Winn, H.E. and B.L. Olla, eds. Behavior of Marine Animals. Vol. 3: cetaceans. Plenum Press, New York.
- Perrin, W.F., Evans, W.E. and D.B. Holts. 1979. Movements of pelagic dolphins (*Stenella* spp.) in the eastern tropical Pacific as indicated by results of tagging, with summary of tagging

